

The Effect of Green Human Resource Management on Organizational Citizenship Behavior Through Affective Commitment: An Evidence from Automotive Component Manufacturing Companies

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to examine the role of green human resource management in influencing organizational citizenship behavior with the mediation role of affective commitment. The object of this research is employees of a manufacturing company engaged in the automotive component sector, located in Karawang Regency. The sampling technique is a multilevel approach by creating standards that follow research needs. The analysis method uses Partial Least Squares, which aims to specifically examine the factors that influence organizational citizenship behavior. Data were obtained using an online questionnaire from employees, and a total of 124 respondents. Data analysis in this study used SmartPLS 3 software. The results showed that green human resource management positively and significantly influences organizational citizenship behavior by mediating affective commitment. This study provides recommendations that the implementation of green human resource management and affective commitment can improve organizational citizenship behavior in automotive component manufacturing companies.

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KEYWORDS: Green Human Resources Management, Organizational Citizenship Behavior, Affective Commitment.

I. INTRODUCTION

The automotive industry is currently growing rapidly, along with the development of vehicle technology that is starting to shift from Internal Combustion Engine (ICE) or combustion engine-powered vehicles to Electric Vehicle (EV) or electric-powered vehicles. ICE technology adds to the burden on the environment due to carbon emissions (CO₂) from the use of fuel oil. Due to environmental problems from CO₂ emissions faced by the automotive industry, this has encouraged a shift to more environmentally friendly EVs due to the use of electric batteries, which have an impact on zero carbon emissions. In addition to the shift in technology towards a more environmentally friendly direction, Human Resource Management (HRM) is also required to support these environmentally friendly practices. To meet expectations regarding environmental issues and implement sustainable business practices, the implementation of Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) practices has begun to be carried out by many companies.

Currently, GHRM has become a major business strategy for substantial organizations where human resource development plays an active role in the work environment. Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) is a company

policy in sustainable human resource management that involves environmental aspects to maintain the sustainability of nature in company management. In the GHRM concept, each company can include environmentally friendly concepts in the operational functions of human resource management, such as Green Competencies (GC), Green Performance Management (GPM), and Green Employee Involvement (GEI) which can influence employee work behavior within the company, or called Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB).

Environmentally based human resource management, or Green Human Resource Management (GHRM), is a company policy in sustainable human resource management that involves environmental aspects to maintain the sustainability of nature in company management. Amid the issue of increasing environmental damage due to the production process, GHRM is needed to minimize this condition. Human Resources Management (HRM) aims to utilize, develop, and research existing human resources and natural resources, enabling their effective and efficient management (Dewi Purnama & Nawangsari, 2019). Management is an effort to organize resources to achieve

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organizational or company goals. As a process to achieve it, careful planning is needed.

One example is an automotive company in Indonesia that pays attention to GHRM. The implementation of GHRM is a form of effort to increase productivity and the company's commitment to maintaining environmental sustainability. GHRM practices are also implemented to support the idea of going green because the company is aware that individual-level pro-environmental behavior or green behavior is needed from all employees to achieve sustainable company performance (Dewi Purnama & Nawangsari, 2019). The role of Human Resources Management (HRM) focuses on transforming ordinary employees into green (environmentally friendly) employees who are centered on achieving a green organizational form and contributing significantly to environmental sustainability (Safroni et al., 2020).

GHRM also proves that organizations that adapt green HRM practices tend to influence their personnel to the concept of their workplace environment with a psychological climate developed by the organization through green HRM initiatives, which allows employees to engage with positive and green attitudes and behaviors regarding the organization's environmental performance benchmarks and standards (Qureshi et al., 2020). GHRM integrates green human resource initiatives and practices for the use of sustainable resources that result in more efficiency, reduce the amount of waste, and increase caring attitudes at work (Ichsan Hadjri et al., 2020). In the GHRM concept, every company can incorporate green concepts into the operational functions of human resource management, such as job design, job analysis, human resource planning, recruitment, selection, orientation, performance management, compensation and benefits, career management, and discipline management (Kurniawan Purnomo, 2021). Success or failure in achieving sales in the automotive industry sector certainly cannot be separated from the role of employees who are the main assets in a company, which are commonly referred to as Human Capital.

Nowadays, GHRM has become a global trend in environmentally-oriented Human Resource Management (HRM). The “green” clause, which is interpreted as environmentally friendly, has become a new competitive advantage offered by the company. Through this environmentally friendly strategy, organizations can build a commitment to use resources more efficiently, transition to the use of renewable energy sources, minimize negative impacts on the environment, and reduce greenhouse gas emissions (Yusuf et al., 2022). GHRM reflects employee competencies in environmental management, which emphasizes the role of HRM in preventing and controlling pollution and protecting the environment in company operations. This includes the implementation of

environmentally friendly HRM functions that result in greater efficiency, lower costs, and better employee involvement.

Implementation of GHRM in a company requires a strong commitment, both from top management who make plans, and from the employee level as the implementer of the plan. Alignment between HRM and GHRM environmental management motivates companies to increase employee commitment to the environment to drive environmental performance (Yusuf et al., 2022). The key to success in all forms of environmental performance activities is to review the participation, willingness, and encouragement of the workforce. So the company should review policies on environmentally friendly behavior in the company's work environment. Implementing environmentally friendly corporate governance will have an impact on the company. And not only limited to that, but more broadly will have an impact on health, safety, and the physical work environment, which will ultimately improve company performance, where the external part of the company will experience changes and increase the productivity of the company itself (Imron & Taswiyah, 2022).

Employee work behavior within a company or Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) is behavior that often goes beyond the employee's job description and involves a series of actions such as helping others, taking on additional responsibilities, spending extra time, advocating for the organization, and speaking up about important organizational issues (Mahrani et al., 2022). OCB behavior in organizations is very important with altruism (concern for the welfare of others without regard for oneself), courtesy, awareness, sportsmanship, and employee benevolence that increase the efficiency and effectiveness of the organization. The definition of OCB is a free individual behavior, not directly or explicitly related to the reward system, but that can improve the effective functioning of the organization (Hidayah & Harnoto, 2018). In modern times, voluntary employee contributions have an impact on organizations because of potential benefits such as increased productivity within the organization.

From a social perspective, organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) refers to obedience or respect, loyalty, and participation. Due to the extra-role nature of organizational citizenship behavior, civil servants are more likely to develop a moral commitment to their organization. Affective commitment is a subset of organizational commitment manifested by employees' strong identification, involvement, and feelings of attachment to the organization (Mahrani et al., 2022). Employees who are effectively committed to the organization identify with the organization to such an extent that they engage in the process of seeking organizational goals and strive for the organization's values and objectives.

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The influence of Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) through affective commitment in an automotive component manufacturing company is the focus of this research. GHRM indicators in this research are focused on Green Competencies, Green Performance Management, and Green Employee Involvement, which still have a large implementation gap in the automotive component manufacturing industry. This research is expected to contribute to the development of knowledge and strengthen the field of HR management in subsequent research. Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) must be maximized through Green Human Resource Management (GHRM). This will show the role of affective commitment in increasing the positive influence of Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) on the company's business processes. Both variables are expected to be able to increase extra-role behavior (beyond their main duties) in employees or Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) in the automotive component manufacturing industry.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Green Human Resource Management

The term Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) derives from the word "Green," meaning "environmentally friendly." Green Management, or environmentally friendly management, is a technique where organizations manage their operations by improving environmental strategies. It is an innovative approach to the performance and responsibilities of Human Resources (HR) within a company, grounded in environmental concepts. GHRM encompasses all activities that involve the development, implementation, and ongoing protection of procedures that prioritize employees within the organization (Imron & Taswiyah, 2022). The concept of Green Human Resource Management relates to the function of Human Resource Management as a key driver in an organization's pursuit of green initiatives. Green Human Resource Management can now address environmental issues. Many companies have implemented GHRM programs through employee training and development. GHRM programs can help companies implement environmentally friendly performance programs by training employees to better appreciate the environment and exploring environmental issues in company operations through recruitment, training, and development, performance management, and providing awards to develop human resources within the company (Imron & Taswiyah, 2022).

GHRM is also defined as the process of utilizing human resources in the workplace to achieve organizational goals through deliberate efforts, while ensuring that the process contributes to environmental sustainability (Yusuf et al., 2022). Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) plays a crucial role for various employees from recruitment and

orientation to their departure. Currently, high employee satisfaction is built & maintained not only with non-physical and social policies, but also with environmentally based practices. "Go green" practices and policies are believed to increase employee engagement and productivity. As a concept that is currently a global trend, Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) has been conceptualized to influence green behavior by employees in the workplace. According to Renwick et al., 2016 in (D. R. Gomes et al., 2024), GHRM practices can be categorized into three levels: (1) GHRM that concerns the development of green competencies in employees through environmentally friendly recruitment, selection, and training; (2) the implementation of GHRM which aims to motivate environmentally friendly employees by rewarding their environmentally friendly performance (green performance management); and (3) GHRM which is related to involving employees in company tasks, empowering them, and creating an environmentally friendly organizational culture (green employee involvement).

Green Competencies

Green Competencies (GC) can be understood as the knowledge, skills, and attitudes that enable the achievement of the mission of minimizing negative impacts on the environment and initiating and implementing actions in line with the principles of sustainable development. The literature uses various keywords related to competency and sustainability, such as GC, green skills, or sustainability competencies, understood as competencies in the field of sustainable development (Graczyk-Kucharska, 2022). GC can be understood as the necessary ecological knowledge, skills, and other socio-economic behaviors that a person possesses to help them behave and act correctly and responsibly to achieve the overall well-being of their immediate environment.

Green Performance Management

Green Performance Management (GPM) is a continuous process of identifying, measuring, and developing individual and team performance, as well as aligning it with organizational goals. Green Performance Management (GPM) refers to a system for guiding employees in aligning their behavior with the organization's environmental goals (Aniqoh et al., 2022). Green performance management practices aim to recognize employees' environmental performance and motivate them to engage in and contribute to the company's environmental activities. This can be translated into green performance standards and green behavior indicators that should serve as benchmarks in employee performance assessments at all levels. Green performance targets, objectives, and responsibilities should be established for employees, and employee achievements in achieving green performance outcomes should be included in

the assessment. Examples of such contributions may include raising awareness and socializing green performance issues among employees, encouraging them to engage in the company's environmental activities, and facilitating environmental management learning (Mandago, 2018).

Green Employee Involvement

Green Employee Involvement (GEI) is a participatory process that uses employee input to increase their commitment to organizational success. Providing green opportunities through employee involvement encourages employees to participate and initiate new ideas for ecological practices, supports them in implementing the organization's environmental goals, and develops a successful environmental management system (Aniqoh et al., 2022). This employee involvement also has a positive impact on the workplace and the surrounding environment. Employee participation can also improve the existing environment. Moreover, if employees are allowed to make decisions and suggestions regarding environmental issues, they will be more willing to voluntarily engage in environmental activities.

Organizational Citizenship Behavior

Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) is a term for employees who place greater value on their work and add value to the company. OCB is also called extra-role behavior because the behavior shown by employees exceeds their primary duties. Compared to in-role behavior, which is carrying out work according to the tasks in the job description, which is associated with extrinsic rewards, extra-role behavior is more associated with intrinsic rewards. Extra-role behavior arises from a feeling of being part of the organization and feeling satisfied when able to do more work in the organization (Ilmih, 2018). In the literature on organizational behavior, it is stated that OCB is a valuable managerial tool for organizations, having a positive effect on individual, group, and organizational performance if managed properly. OCB is the willingness of employees to take on roles that exceed their primary roles in an organization, so it is called extra-role behavior. The success of an organization is when its members do not only carry out their main tasks, but are also willing to carry out extra tasks, such as the willingness to work together, help each other, provide input, play an active role, provide extra services, and are willing to use their work time effectively (Lestari et al., 2018).

OCB is a discretionary behavior that is not part of an employee's formal work obligations but supports the effective functioning of the organization. OCB develops in line with how much the organization pays attention to employee contributions, resulting in employees having a positive perception of the organization and providing feedback by engaging in OCB. Furthermore, organizational

behavior can maximize the efficiency and productivity of both employees and the organization, ultimately contributing to the effective functioning of an organization (Ilmih, 2018). OCB provides a way of managing employees through interdependence between work unit members that improves collective outcomes and eliminates the need for the organization to allocate limited resources to basic maintenance functions, freeing up resources for greater efficiency and enhancing capabilities (Amalia et al., 2021). Employees who engage in OCB behavior can perform their work anywhere, so they don't need to wait for a specific company to become large. If a company has OCB behavior, its performance will certainly be better compared to companies that do not. Successful companies rely heavily on the participation of all employees to perform well for their company. Therefore, strong companies naturally need employees who can go above and beyond their assigned duties. Therefore, Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) plays a crucial role in a company's growth and development (Margahana, 2020).

Affective Commitment

The definition of affective commitment is an individual's willingness to remain in an organization characterized by an emotional attachment to the organization, identification with the organization's values and goals, and involvement in the organization (Prasetyaninghayu, 2018). This shows how the employee relates to feelings of belonging, connection, and dedication from employees. Affective commitment can improve the performance of Human Resources so that emotional or psychological attachment in employees is needed in advancing the company, such as moral support and accepting the values in the organization, as well as the determination from within to serve the organization. According to Greenberg in Prasetyaninghayu (2018) explained that affective commitment can be interpreted as the strength of a person's desire to work for the organization because he or she agrees with it and wants to do so. Affective commitment can be interpreted as a person's strength to work in an organization, because they agree and want to do the job.

According to Ramirez-Solis & Ilián Baños-Monroy (2015), affective commitment is defined as the sense of belonging that an individual feels for organizational goals and values, meaning that an individual's sense of belonging to the organization, pride, and empathy for the values and goals of the organization. Affective commitment is related to emotions, identification, and individual involvement in an organization. Members who have this commitment have an emotional attachment to the organization that is reflected through involvement and feelings of pleasure and enjoyment of their role in the organization. Employees who have affective commitment will be more valuable to the company because they have involved emotional factors, so that

employees with affective commitment will work with a feeling of pleasure and enjoy their role in the company (Prasetyaninghayu, 2018). Employees with affective commitment truly want to be employees in the company concerned, so they have the desire to use optimal efforts to achieve company goals. Employees with continuance commitment tend to do their duties because they avoid financial and other losses, so they only make suboptimal efforts. According to Meyer, Allen and Smith in Prasetyaninghayu (2018), it is explained that to assess affective commitment, it can be measured by, among other things, spending the rest of one's career, being proud of the organization, being attached to the organization, being emotionally attached, having great meaning and having a strong feeling for the organization.

III. HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

Green Competencies on Affective Commitment

Commitment can be defined as the bond that characterizes an employee's relationship with an organization, meaning it influences the strength of membership in a company. Meanwhile, affective commitment is an employee's emotional bond to their organization and is said to predict dedication and loyalty through a high sense of belonging and identification (J. F. S. Gomes et al., 2023). Previous research has found a positive and significant relationship between HR practices and affective commitment (Yang, 2012, in J. F. S. Gomes et al., 2023). Other research has shown that HR management development is associated with higher levels of commitment and engagement through the mediating role of psychological contracts. Higher levels of relational psychological contracts are associated with higher levels of commitment and engagement (Bal et al., 2013, in J. F. S. Gomes et al., 2023).

Research investigating the relationship between affective commitment and green competency practices is still very rare. Recent studies on HR practices may address this gap, as the ecological dimension of Green Human Resources Management has found limited support for the view that green competency practices influence employee affective commitment. In line with previous empirical findings, the following hypothesis is formulated:

H1 = Green Competencies has a positive and significant effect on Affective Commitment.

Green Performance Management on Affective Commitment

Green performance management practices aim to recognize employees' environmental performance and motivate them to engage in and contribute to the company's environmental activities. Environmental-based feedback from supervisors or managers will help improve employees' knowledge, skills, and abilities, which can increase their motivation to engage in environmental responsibility

(Aniqoh et al., 2022). It is expected that when top management is committed to the environment and the green intellectual capital of the organization where they work, they will lead the implementation of GHRM by attracting, developing, and retaining environmentally conscious employees, facilitating GHRM implementation, and making their human resources more aligned and committed to the company's green goals (D. R. Gomes et al., 2024).

Social identity theory supports the theoretical framework for rationalizing the relationship between GHRM and affective commitment. It is assumed that employees who hold positive organizational values are motivated to develop affective bonds with the organization. Referring to the principles of social identity theory, organizations that actively promote green initiatives, such as GHRM, tend to enhance their corporate image and reputation. Green performance management practices foster a strong psychological bond between employees and the company, so that employees tend to identify with the company and develop a deeper affective commitment (D. R. Gomes et al., 2024). In line with previous empirical findings, the following hypothesis is formulated:

H2 = Green Performance Management has a positive and significant effect on Affective Commitment.

Green Employee Involvement on Affective Commitment

Green Human Resource Management refers to the use of sustainable environmental practices and increased employee commitment to environmental sustainability issues. Positive employee perceptions of GHRM practices impact employee engagement in the workplace, and organizational leaders play a crucial role in promoting GHRM practices and creating a culture that supports sustainable environmental management (Dira et al., 2024). Research shows that green employee involvement increases Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB). Employees who are more active in environmental engagement, such as volunteering for environmental initiatives or encouraging coworkers to do the same, are more likely to engage in activities that contribute to the environment (Cheema et al., 2020, in Malokani et al., 2023).

Environmentally friendly employee participation or involvement can establish a social norm where all workers are expected to behave in an environmentally friendly manner. This social norm can inspire OCB towards the environment and increase the likelihood of other workers adopting similar behavior (Malokani et al., 2023). The practice of green employee involvement fosters a strong psychological bond between employees and the company, so that employees tend to identify with the company and develop a deeper affective commitment. In line with previous empirical findings, the following hypothesis is formulated:

H3 = Green Employee Involvement has a positive and significant effect on Affective Commitment.

Affective Commitment on Organizational Citizenship Behavior

One factor influencing the emergence of Organizational Citizenship Behavior in employees is the affective commitment they have to the company. Affective commitment is an employee's emotional tendency to identify with the company's values and goals, behave loyally to the company, have a strong emotional dependence on the company, and strive hard to dedicate themselves to the company's success (Zao et al., 2022, in Rahman & Frianto, 2024).

Employees with a high affective commitment will have a close emotional connection with the company, which will encourage them to continuously strive to provide the best for the company's interests (Jufrizen et al., 2023). Employees with Organizational Citizenship Behavior will help them perform their work effectively and efficiently, enabling them to make greater contributions to the company, which in turn can help the company grow (Fatmasari & Rozaq, 2023). In line with previous empirical findings, the following hypothesis is formulated:

H4 = Affective Commitment has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior.

Green Competencies on Organizational Citizenship Behavior through Affective Commitment

Green Competencies focus on employee sensitivity to environmental conservation and sustainable development to foster Organizational Citizenship Behavior in the workplace (Cabral & Dhar, 2021, in Nurhakim & Puspa, 2023). Green competencies are part of HRM practices to enhance employee capabilities and lead to Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB). Improving employee capabilities will enhance their emotional bond with their organization and is said to predict dedication and loyalty through a strong sense of belonging and identification, also known as affective commitment (J. F. S. Gomes et al., 2023).

Research conducted by Saputro & Nawangsari (2021) found that green competence has a significant positive effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior for the Environment (OCBE). Research by Kharismasyah & Bagis (2019) found that affective commitment mediates a positive and significant effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) in linking distributive justice and procedural justice. In line with previous empirical findings, the following hypothesis is formulated:

H5 = Green Competencies has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior through the mediation of Affective Commitment.

Green Performance Management on Organizational Citizenship Behavior through Affective Commitment

Research by Aniqoh et al. (2022) found that Green Performance Management has a positive and significant

impact on Organizational Citizenship Behavior for the Environment (OCBE). Assessing employees' environmental activities helps improve some of their green capabilities, knowledge, and skills, which in turn helps them become more actively involved in environmental projects. Green Performance Management encompasses issues related to environmental issues and company policies, and also focuses on the use of environmental responsibility (Mandago, 2018).

Some companies address performance management issues by establishing company-wide environmental performance standards, green information systems, and audits to obtain useful data on environmental performance (Marcus & Fremeth, 2010, in Mandago, 2018). Green performance management practices foster a strong psychological bond between employees and the company, leading to employees identifying with the company and developing a deeper affective commitment (D. R. Gomes et al., 2024). In line with previous empirical findings, the following hypothesis is formulated:

H6 = Green Performance Management has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior through the mediation of Affective Commitment.

Green Employee Involvement on Organizational Citizenship Behavior through Affective Commitment

Green Employee Involvement (EI) provides employees with the opportunity to participate in organizational greening, which can enhance their knowledge and ability to address environmental issues, ultimately contributing to Organizational Citizenship Behavior for the Environment (OCBE) (Boiral & Paillé, 2012 in Nurhakim & Puspa, 2023). The greater employee interest in environmental activities, the more directly they contribute to environmental management. This employee involvement also positively impacts the workplace and the surrounding environment. Employee participation can also improve the existing environment (Aniqoh et al., 2022).

Research by Aniqoh et al. (2022) found that Green Employee Involvement has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior for the Environment (OCBE). Environmentally friendly practices, such as creating forums and opportunities for employees to engage in environmental activities and enabling them to make and participate in decisions related to solving environmental problems, help increase commitment within the organization. Employees with high affective commitment will have a close emotional connection with the company, leading them to continuously strive to provide the best for the company's interests (Jufrizen et al., 2023). In line with previous empirical findings, the following hypothesis is formulated:

H7 = Green Employee Involvement has a positive and significant effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior through the mediation of Affective Commitment.

Conceptual Framework

The research model is designed to explain three independent variables whose influence on the dependent variable will be analysed through a mediating variable. The graphical model describes the relationship of the three independent variables, namely: green competencies, green performance management, and green employee involvement, to the dependent variable, namely: organizational citizenship behavior, through a mediating variable, namely: affective commitment.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

IV. RESEARCH METHOD

This quantitative research will analyse the implications of green competencies, green performance management, and green employee involvement on organizational citizenship behavior through affective commitment. This research was conducted at an automotive component manufacturing company in Karawang. This research method used Partial Least Square (PLS). The independent variables were green competencies, green performance management, and green employee involvement. The dependent variable was organizational citizenship behavior. The mediating variable was affective commitment, which connects the independent variables with the dependent variable.

The research was analysed using the Partial Least Square (PLS) method and a purposive sampling approach. This method is adapted to the research needs and can display more details about the feasibility of variable indicators (Ghozali, 2020). A more detailed analysis can be carried out to test hypotheses against the research variables. The test tools used were outer loading, validity & reliability tests, R-Square, and Partial T-test. Outer loading was used to examine the representation of variable indicators with a value > 0.7. Validity and reliability tests used Cronbach Alpha (> 0.7), Composite Reliability (> 0.7), and AVE (> 0.5). R-Square indicates the extent to which the independent variable determines the dependent variable. The T-test was used to test the hypotheses developed and the influence between variables based on the conceptual framework.

The sample used in this study uses a measure of the number of categories, as explained by Roscoe (in Nur Fadilah Amin et al., 2023), that if the sample is divided into categories (for example: male-female, civil servant-private

sector, etc.), then the number of sample members for each category is at least 30. There are 4 categories in this study, namely: gender, education, length of service, and job level. The number of sample members for each category is 30, so the minimum sample size is: 4 x 30 = 120. In this study, the research instrument used is a questionnaire distributed via Google Forms to 124 employees who work at a manufacturing company in the Karawang Regency area. This study uses four scales, namely: 1 (strongly disagree), 2 (disagree), 3 (agree), and 4 (strongly agree), which are used to collect data.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Respondent Profile

The respondents of this study were 124 people who were employees of an automotive component manufacturing company in Karawang Regency. The total number of respondents was 85% male and 15% female. 84% of respondents had a high school education or equivalent, 5% a diploma, 10% a bachelor's degree, and 1% a master's degree. 24% of respondents had work experience of 0-5 years, 10% a 6-10 years, and 66% a >10 years. The respondents' job levels were driver 5%, security 6%, operator 75%, line leader 3%, team leader 1%, staff 7%, section head 1%, department/division head 2%.

Item	Description	Respondents	%
Gender	Male	106	85%
	Female	18	15%
Education	Senior High School	105	84%
	Associate's Degree	6	5%
	Bachelor's Degree	12	10%
	Master's Degree	1	1%
Years of Service	0 – 5 years	30	24%
	6 – 10 years	12	10%
	> 10 years	82	66%
Job Title	Driver	5	5%
	Security	7	6%
	Operator	93	75%
	Line Leader	4	3%
	Team Leader	1	1%
	Staff	9	7%
	Section Head	1	1%
	Dept/Division Head	3	2%

Figure 2. Respondent Profile

Validity and Reliability Test

The research variables were analysed using the Partial Least Squares (PLS) method by identifying variable indicators, conducting validity and reliability tests, conducting the R-square test, and conducting the T-test for hypothesis testing. The process began by examining all variable indicators with outer loading values >0.7. An outer loading value >0.7 indicates convergent validity, and if the outer loading value is <0.7, the construct should be removed from the analysis (Ghozali, 2020). All variable indicators used in this study had outer loading values >0.7, thus adequately describing their latent variables and being suitable for use in the research model. The indicators used in

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green competencies, green performance management, green employee involvement, organizational citizenship behavior, and affective commitment all contribute to this research model.

Table 1. Outer Loading Value

Variable	Indicator	Outer Loading	Description
Green Competencies (X1)	GC1	0,863	Valid
	GC2	0,898	Valid
	GC3	0,848	Valid
	GC4	0,765	Valid
Green Performance Management (X2)	GPM1	0,919	Valid
	GPM2	0,951	Valid
	GPM3	0,931	Valid
	GPM4	0,719	Valid
Green Employee Involvement (X3)	GE11	0,907	Valid
	GE12	0,900	Valid
	GE13	0,894	Valid
	GE15	0,755	Valid
Organizational Citizenship Behavior (Y)	OCB1	0,906	Valid
	OCB2	0,819	Valid
	OCB3	0,940	Valid
	OCB4	0,905	Valid
Affective Commitment (Z)	AC1	0,863	Valid
	AC2	0,898	Valid
	AC3	0,848	Valid
	AC4	0,765	Valid

Validity testing was conducted to verify the research instrument or questionnaire. Reliability testing was conducted to determine whether the measuring instrument accurately and consistently measured data based on respondents' responses (Ghozali, 2020). The indicators used were Cronbach's Alpha >0.7 (valid), Composite Reliability >0.7 (valid), and Average Variance Extracted >0.5 (valid value for each variable). The AVE value for all study variables was >0.5, indicating validity, while the Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability values for all study variables were >0.7, indicating reliability.

The R-square test, or coefficient of determination, was conducted to demonstrate the extent to which the independent variable influences the dependent variable (Ghozali, 2020). The R-square result from this study was 0.65, or 65%, for organizational citizenship behavior, indicating that the influence of green competencies, green performance management, and green employee involvement on organizational citizenship behavior was 65%, with the remaining 35% being attributed to external variables. The R Square results from this study obtained a value of 0.72 or 72% on affective commitment, thus indicating that the influence of green competencies, green performance management, green employee involvement, and affective commitment on organizational citizenship behavior was 72% and the remaining 28% was outside the research variables.

Table 2. R-square Test

Variable	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Affective Commitment	0,719	0,712
Organizational Citizenship Behavior	0,651	0,648

Direct Effect Hypothesis Testing

The direct effect hypothesis is tested by measuring path coefficients, which then yield T-statistics and P-values. If the T-statistics value is >1.96 (T-table significance 5%), the effect is significant. If the P-values obtained between constructs are <0.05, the hypothesis is accepted (Ghozali, 2020).

1. The direct effect of green competencies on affective commitment has a T-statistics value of 2.367 (>1.96) and a P-value of 0.018 (<0.05). This indicates that the effect of green competencies on affective commitment is positive and significant, and H1 is accepted.
2. The direct effect of green performance management on affective commitment has a T-statistics value of 1.713 (<1.96) and a P-value of 0.087 (>0.05). This indicates that the effect of green performance management on affective commitment is positive but not significant, and H2 is rejected.
3. The direct effect of green employee involvement on affective commitment has a T-statistic value of 1.770 (<1.96) and a P-value of 0.077 (>0.05), indicating that the effect of green employee involvement on affective commitment is positive but not significant, and H3 is rejected.
4. The direct effect of affective commitment on organizational citizenship behavior has a T-statistic value of 12.192 (>1.96) and a P-value of 0.000 (<0.05), indicating that the effect of green competencies on affective commitment is positive and significant, and H4 is accepted.

Table 3. Direct Hypothesis Test

Variablel	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T-Statistic ((O-STDEV))	P Values
Green Competencies -> Affective Commitment	0,294	0,296	0,124	2,367	0,018
Green Performance Management -> Affective Commitment	0,311	0,273	0,175	1,770	0,077
Green Employee Involvement -> Affective Commitment	0,335	0,371	0,195	1,713	0,087
Affective Commitment -> Organizational Citizenship Behavior	0,807	0,800	0,066	12,192	0,000

Indirect Effect Hypothesis Testing

The indirect effect hypothesis is tested by measuring the Specific Indirect Effects, which then yields T-statistics and P-values through the bootstrapping procedure. If the T-statistics value is >1.96 (T-table significance 5%), the effect is significant. If the P-values obtained between constructs are <0.05, the hypothesis is accepted (Ghozali, 2020).

1. The indirect effect of green competencies on organizational citizenship behavior through affective

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commitment has a T-statistics value of 2.307 (>1.96) and a P-value of 0.021 (<0.05). This means the effect of green competencies on organizational citizenship behavior through affective commitment is positive and significant, and H5 is accepted.

2. The indirect effect of green performance management on organizational citizenship behavior through affective commitment has a T-statistics value of 1.708 (<1.96) and a P-value of 0.088 (>0.05). This means the effect of green performance management on organizational citizenship behavior through affective commitment is positive but not significant, and H6 is rejected.
3. The indirect effect of green employee involvement on organizational citizenship behavior through affective commitment has a T Statistics value of 1.743 (<1.96) and P Values of 0.082 (>0.05), so the effect of green employee involvement on organizational citizenship behavior through affective commitment is positive but not significant, and H7 is rejected.

Table 4. Indirect Hypothesis Test

Variable	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O-STDEV)	P Values
Green Competencies -> Affective Commitment -> Organizational Citizenship Behavior	0,237	0,237	0,103	2,307	0,021
Green Performance Management -> Affective Commitment -> Organizational Citizenship Behavior	0,251	0,219	0,144	1,743	0,082
Green Employee Involvement -> Affective Commitment -> Organizational Citizenship Behavior	0,270	0,296	0,158	1,708	0,088

To visualize the results of the bootstrapping procedure from this research, the image below represents the R-square values, the path coefficient values on the influence path, and the outer loading values for each indicator variable.

Table 5. Bootstrapping Analysis Results

Discussion

The research aims to demonstrate the influence of green human resources measured through the variables of green competencies, green performance management, and green employee involvement on organizational citizenship behavior through affective commitment as mediation in automotive component manufacturing companies. Based on the data analysis that has been done, it can be seen that green competencies have a positive and significant influence on affective commitment indicated by H1 being accepted, affective commitment has a positive and significant influence on organizational citizenship behavior indicated by H4 being accepted, and green competencies have a positive and significant influence on organizational citizenship behavior through affective commitment mediation indicated by H5 being accepted. This indicates that the higher the knowledge, skills, and attitudes of employees, the higher the emotional bond, dedication, and loyalty of employees to the company, so that they can minimize negative impacts on the environment and initiate and implement actions that are in line with the principles of sustainable development. The higher the knowledge, skills, and attitudes of employees, the higher the extra-role behavior, namely, behavior given by employees beyond their main duties.

Green performance management has a positive but insignificant effect on affective commitment, indicated by H2 being rejected, green employee involvement has a positive but insignificant effect on affective commitment, indicated by H3 being rejected, green performance management has a positive but insignificant effect on organizational citizenship behavior through mediation of affective commitment, indicated by H6 being rejected, and green employee involvement has a positive but insignificant effect on organizational citizenship behavior through mediation of affective commitment, indicated by H7 being rejected. This indicates that green performance management, as a continuous process to identify, measure, and develop individual and team performance and align their performance with organizational goals, has no relationship with emotional bonds, dedication, and loyalty of employees to the company or extra-role behavior. Likewise, green opportunities through employee involvement, encouraging employees to participate and initiate new ideas for ecological practices, implementing organizational environmental goals and developing a successful environmental management system have no relationship with emotional bonds, dedication, and loyalty of employees to the company or extra role behavior, namely behavior given by employees beyond their main duties.

VI. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The limitation of this research lies in its analysis of factors affecting green competencies, green performance management, and green employee involvement, which

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affected organizational citizenship behavior through the mediating role of affective commitment. This limitation was caused by limited research variables, although the determination coefficients of the variable green competencies exhibited a positive effect on the affective commitment to improve organizational citizenship behavior. This research could be further extended by using other variables such as green recruitment, green compensation, among others. Future research could also involve other mediating or intervening variables required by organizations to achieve their vision, mission, and target. It is also possible to examine different industries, such as the field of education, tourism, or service-based industries.

Companies in automotive component manufacturing always need new ideas and innovation from their employees to seize the dynamic business challenges. Companies should be able to implement a human resource strategy to implement green human resource management in order to maintain affective commitment and organizational citizenship behavior. It should also be noted that green performance management and green employee involvement are inseparable from green human resource management strategy, although this study did not find its positive effect on affective commitment and organizational citizenship behavior. Organizational citizenship behavior reflects the green human resource management strategy implemented to all employees equally, usually in the form of higher knowledge, skills, and attitudes of employees, which will lead to higher extra-role behavior, namely, behavior given by employees beyond their main duties.

Company or organization management should be aware that, at a certain level, the implementation of green human resource management may rely on factors provided by companies to their employees. In this regard, factors mentioned earlier in this paper may result in organizational citizenship behavior that exceeds the company's expectations. Employees with a high level of affective commitment tend to have higher motivation to improve their organizational citizenship behavior. Such employees may have a positive effect on their team and departments in the company. Eventually, employees may exhibit higher organizational citizenship behavior and work together to achieve the company's vision, mission, and goals.

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